

CONTENT CHARACTERISTICS OF A DICTIONARY OF WOMEN'S CLOTHING IN COMPARATIVE LANGUAGES

Gulruh Soxibbek qizi Tillaboyeva

Teacher of the Department of Primary Education Methodology
Fergana State University

The structure of word naming in English and Tajik languages of clothing dictionary and at the same time the problem of its analysis becomes complicated as soon as we turn to derivative words. "Unlike ordinary words, English derivations of clothing words are determined from the point of view of their belonging to the noun, although homonymy of affixes and conversion of parts of speech significantly reduce the ability of English affixes to indicate parts of speech" [Meshkov O.D., 1986, 121 p.].

The addition of a word-forming affix complicates the structure of the English noun, but it still retains its relative simplicity, since the affix itself, or rather the suffix itself, does not add any morphological influence to the word. does not include a feature, except to show the parts. speech Another important factor in the problems of word formation is the separation of the word-forming affix in the naming of the clothing dictionary and, therefore, the classification of a given noun as a derivative. The factor for English is that the language has a lot of assimilated words with word-forming affixes as well as clothing names, but the roots of these words are not. independent use in modern English. Such words work in parallel with words in which, after the affix is removed, a part equal to the full-valued word remains.

In addition, P.M. Karashchuk in his book "Word formation of the English language" focuses on dividing all derived nouns into formations using agentive suffixes and abstract suffixes [P.M. Karashchuk, 1977, p. 302].

Of all the demonstrative suffixes of nouns, the suffix -er is the most

effective, but when applied to the names of articles of clothing under study, the suffix -er is not an auxiliary, but an instrumental form that has been formed since the early English period. will have no.

In fact, in the following words - what stands out as a suffix of the word does not determine any semantic relationship with the remaining parts of the word after subtracting what is taken as a suffix of the word:

- halter (belt-like) can be divided into the main stop + suffix - for example. However, the meaning of the English noun stop (stop, stop) does not depend in any way when the suffix -er is added to the item of clothing. The only possible possibility is that the origin of the root halt is from the German verb halten (to hold, to hold), because the meaning of the verb can be connected in one way or another to the meaning of a piece of clothing. (the purpose of a bra is to support the breast); - shim (shim, shim shim, ezor), it seems that this word can be divided into trous + -er, sin + band + ak.

Thus, based on the above analysis, it is more correct to assume that the words halter, pants, srencher in English, although they contain the false suffix - er, are not derived, but are simpler in structure. will be because for the modern linguistic mind. such words are indivisible.

- sneakers (sneakers - shoe sport) sneak (from the verb sneakr (sneakr)) +er - a shoe that can be silently moved on someone; - slipper (slipper) slir (from the verb sliron (throw, put on) + er - a shoe that is easy to put on the foot; - drawers (long socks, underpants, tagpushak, zerpush, ilisi tag) -> draw (pull) + er clothes to be put on the feet; - trainers (sneakers-shoes) to train (exercise) + er - shoes for sports; suffix -ee originally in English legal and administrative entered as part of the term, but is not widely used as a word-forming element on English soil. This suffix is found only in one item of clothing, the word bootie (booties). primary meaning, as a noun suffix with the meaning of a person as the subject of action (for example, in the words employee, candidate).

So, in this case, the meaning of the suffix -ee is blurred, so this word should not be considered as a derivative either. As noted by Academician V.V. Vinogradov, "affixes that have lost their meaning, become ineffective and are accepted only as signs of this or that sentence cease to be affixes and retain only the characteristic of differentiation" [V.V. Vinogradov, 1952, 243p]. It is known that a compound word is a word formed by joining two or more roots. In English, complex words for clothes, like other complex words, are formed according to certain patterns. These models differ significantly from each other in many features. Thus, there are models from which the hundreds and thousands of words that make up the vocabulary of a language are created. Finally, there may be models based on which only a few or even one word is created. The importance of each individual model is that within some of them, different semantic types with different relationships between components can work, while other models, in turn, can only generate words of the same type.

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